
Long-term Durability of Seawater Electrolysis for Hydrogen: From Catalysts to Systems

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Abstract: Direct electrochemical seawater splitting is a renewable, scalable, and potentially economic approach for green hydrogen production. However, issues related to low durability caused by complex ions in seawater pose great challenges for its industrialization. In this review, a mechanistic analysis of durability issues of electrolytic seawater splitting is discussed. We critically analyze the development of seawater electrolysis and identify the durability challenges at both the anode and cathode. Particular emphasis is paid to elucidate rational strategies for designing electrocatalysts/electrodes/interfaces with long lifetimes in realistic seawater including inducing passivating anion layers, preferential OH⁻ adsorption, employing anti-corrosion materials, fabricating protective layers, immobilizing Cl⁻ on the surface of electrocatalysts, tailoring Cl⁻ adsorption sites, inhibiting binding of OH⁻ to Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, inhibiting adherence of Mg and Ca hydroxides precipitation, and co-synthesis of nano-sized Mg hydroxides. Synthesis methods of electrocatalysts/electrodes and innovations in electrolyzer are also discussed. Furthermore, the prospects for developing seawater splitting technologies for clean hydrogen generation are summarized. We found that researchers have changed the attitude towards Cl⁻ ions from “hate” to accept to utilize, as well as more attention to cathodic reaction and electrolyzers, which is conducive to accelerate the commercialization of seawater electrolysis.

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1. Introduction

Electrocatalytic seawater splitting to generate hydrogen (H_2) from renewable sources is a promising strategy to address the increasing demand for readily transportable and storable forms of energy.^[1] Analogous to freshwater splitting, seawater electrolysis mainly consists of two half-reactions: hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) at the cathode and oxygen evolution reaction (OER) at the anode (on the left side of Figure 1). However, electrolyzing seawater faces additional and intricate challenges owing to the containing of over 90 kinds of ions, which deactivates the electrocatalysts, and even leads to severe corrosion.^[2] Therefore, since 1975, when it was first realized that seawater can be used to directly produce hydrogen,^[3] seawater splitting (SWS) for H_2 generation has not reached the level of practical application (Figure 1). However, in the past two decades, SWS for H_2 has developed fast benefitting from the rapid evolution of nanomaterials and nanotechnologies.^[1d, 1f, 4] For example, in 2011, the most efficient Mn-based electrocatalyst was developed and shown to have an impressive durability of 4300 h under the current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} for OER in seawater,^[4a] and a non-noble metal based electrode for HER, which displays stable performance for up to 2000 h in 1 M NaOH and seawater was reported in 2023.^[4d] In addition to the remarkable progress made in electrocatalysts, significant improvements have been made in designing new and improved electrolyzers. For instance, anion exchange membrane (AEM), and proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolyzers that operate using a saline water feed were described by Strasser^[1f] in 2018 and Logan^[4i] in 2021, respectively.

Despite of the important advancements that have been made thus far, industrialization of SWS has not yet been realized. Two major impediments in large-scale seawater electrolysis are low activity and poor durability, with the latter being particularly crucial in limiting applications to industrial scale generation of H_2 . As shown in Figure 1, batch-type cells,^[4c, 5] as well as PEM^[4f, 6] and AEM^[7] electrolyzers have significantly inferior durability including short lifetime and low current density in SWS in contrast to pure water. This problem is especially relevant to membrane electrolyzers. Two approaches have been developed to avoid challenges associated with seawater electrolysis that are termed indirect seawater electrolysis and direct seawater electrolysis. By incorporating extensive water purification systems into the SWS electrolyzer, high purity water is achieved for indirect seawater electrolysis. However, this approach imposes considerable costs associated with construction and maintenance of the purification system. It has been reported that the capital cost of the desalination system can be up to 7% of the electrolyzer, which cannot be ignored.^[8] Moreover, advances in electrocatalysis technology and electrolyzer design will further decrease the cost of direct SWS.^[9] Consequently, direct seawater electrolysis has received major attention. It would be a promising route for direct SWS by using saline water directly, developing efficient and durable electrocatalysts, and utilizing improved membrane electrolyzers.

Recently, many reviews and books about SWS have been published.^[1e, 8b, 10] For example, Tong et al. clearly outlined the challenges for efficient direct electrolysis of saline water and discussed potential approaches to highly active and selective HER or OER electrode materials/catalysts for electrolysis of low-grade and saline water.^[1e] These accounts have focused primarily on the SWS

activities and selectivity of various catalyst families. However, electrocatalysts durability issues have received relatively less attention. Importantly, a mechanistic foundation is required to design catalysts that have enhanced lifetimes in SWS. Therefore, in this review, we aim to provide valuable insights into the mechanism underlying the poor durability observed in SWS. For this purpose, we first provide a concise overview of the development of SWS, including the design and properties of electrocatalysts and electrolyzers. Next, we comprehensively summarize challenges related to durability of both anode and cathode materials in SWS (Section 2). This is followed by discussions of the development and applications of rational strategies employed to enhance the durability of catalysts/interfaces for the OER (Section 3) and HER (Section 4). Obviously, researchers have changed the attitude from “hate” to accept to utilize towards Cl^- ions, as well as more attention on cathodic reaction. Then, we discuss methods for the synthesis of electrocatalysts with improved durability (Section 5). Additionally, four notable innovations in the design of electrolyzers used in SWS are highlighted (Section 6). Finally, we emphasize the issues need to be taken into closer consideration for standardization of lab studies and industrialization of seawater electrolysis in the future. We hope that this critical review could be helpful in achieving a better understanding of durable

Figure 1. A brief timeline of seawater splitting (SWS) development and durability records with/without seawater for batch-type cell water electrolysis, proton exchange membrane (PEM) water electrolysis and anion exchange membrane (AEM) water electrolysis (J represents a certain current density. For example, J₁₀₀ represents under the current density of 100 mA cm⁻²).

electrolysis in seawater and provide a promising pathway for the design of electrocatalysts as well as electrolyzers with high stability.

2. Durability Challenges of Electrocatalysts for Seawater Electrolysis

Issues associated with the poor durability of electrocatalytic materials in seawater electrolysis arise from the two half-reactions in the overall process including the OER at the anode and the HER at the cathode (Figure 2).

Due to the existence of abundant Cl^- in seawater, it deteriorates the performance of electrocatalysts for the seawater electrolysis. First, chlorine evolution reaction (CER) is competitive to OER that forms toxic chlorine or hypochlorite ions.^[11] Second, the strong coordination interaction between Cl^- and active sites of the electrocatalysts accelerates catalyst corrosion and leads to poor durability.^[12]

Different from OER which is subject to the competitive CER, the HER electrocatalysts involve less attention to enhance the selectivity because the thermodynamic potentials for competing reactions are not as close than for the OER and CER, such as -0.48 V (vs. standard hydrogen electrode (SHE)) for $\text{B}(\text{OH})_3/\text{BH}_4^-$ and -0.53 V (vs. SHE) for CO_2/CO .^[2, 13] Near the cathode, the local pH increase during seawater electrolysis can lead to precipitation of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$, which occurs when $\text{pH} \geq \text{ca. } 9.5$, leading the degradation of active sites.^[14] The abundant Cl^- may lead to a significant deactivation and dissolution of active sites, especially for Pt group metals.^[15] Besides, the cathodic electrochemical deposition may also occur at specific potential windows due to the existence of other dissolved metal ions, such as Cu and Pb ions.^[16] Furthermore, on both electrodes, other impurities including small particles and bacteria/microbes could poison catalysts by physically blocking the active sites.

3. Rational Design Strategies toward Durable OER Catalysts/Interfaces for SWS

To address the challenges at the anode, Dionigi et al. firstly outlined an alkaline design criterion for highly selective OER electrocatalysts to suppress Cl_2 or ClO^- formation.^[11] Thus, most seawater electrolysis processes are conducted in solutions of elevated pH or at AEMs rather than in natural seawater that is nearly neutral. In this section, we describe 6 strategies that have been devised to effectively design highly durable OER

Figure 2. Durability challenges of electrocatalysts for SWS. Challenges at the anode are primarily stem from Cl^- corrosion and competition with chlorine evolution reaction (CER) while at the cathode, challenges include Cl^- corrosion, as well as the deposition of impurities such as hydroxides and metal ions.

electrocatalysts in seawater (Figure 3). These are surface repulsion of Cl^- (including inducing passivating anion layers and preferential OH^- adsorption), chemically inertness to Cl^- (including employing anti-corrosion materials and fabricating protective layers), and selective adsorption of Cl^- (including immobilizing Cl^- on the surface and tailoring Cl^- adsorption sites). It should be strongly stated that there is little to no direct evidence of surface charges on the electrodes under practical potential of OER. Therefore, in the spirit of rigor, the strategy of surface repulsion of Cl^- should be regarded as a reasonable hypothesis.

Among these strategies, selective adsorption of Cl^- represents the latest advancement, facilitated by the development of advanced in situ characterization techniques. Employing these techniques will provide direct information on transformations occurring during HER/OER and help to understand the decay mechanisms during long-term durability tests. Additionally, the practical process of SWS is accompanied by salt accumulation. In this context, adsorbing Cl^- on the specific site of electrocatalysts that does not significantly hinder performance or may even enhance OER is desired.

3.1. Surface Repulsion of Cl⁻

Inducing passivating anion layers

Anion-rich surfaces generated in situ under an OER positive bias have shown to effectively repel Cl⁻ (Figure 3a). For example, Kuang et al. demonstrated that a NiFe/NiS_x/Ni anode is both active and stable during seawater electrolysis. The NiS_x layer in this material is responsible for corrosion resistance.^[4b] Derived from the NiS_x anodizing, the sulfate as well as carbonate species in the electrolyte, brings the anode into negative charge, which repels the Cl⁻ in seawater. Furthermore, Ma et al. investigated the critical role of a surface sulfate additive in stabilizing Ni-based electrodes during alkaline SWS.^[17] This work provided a new view that adsorbed SO₄²⁻ from exotic electrolytes was also applicable. Also, Li et al. reported that, in contrast to CO₃²⁻ absorbed from the electrolyte, CO₃²⁻ generated in situ by self-transformation of a NiFe oxalate electrode safeguards active sites against Cl⁻ induced decay even at ampere-level current densities.^[18]

Similar to SO₄²⁻^[4b, 19] and CO₃²⁻^[4e, 18], in situ formed PO₄³⁻^[20], NO₃⁻^[21], MoO₄²⁻^[4c, 22], SeO_x⁻^[22b, 23] and BO₂⁻^[24] have been found to inhibit the Cl⁻ corrosion of the anode during the OER process. For instance, Liu et al. described a CoFe PBA/Co₂P anode that catalyzes alkaline seawater oxidation at 200–2000 mA cm⁻² for over 1000 h without corrosion.^[20a] The PO₄³⁻ and Fe(CN)₆³⁻ layer produced by Co₂P and CoFePBA electrode repels the Cl⁻ synergistically through electrostatic repulsion. In addition, Zhang et al. prepared Fe₂P/Ni_{1.5}Co_{1.5}N/Ni₂P hierarchical nanostructure arrays supported on Ni foam (NF), which require only 1.742 V to afford a current density of 500 mA cm⁻² in 1 M KOH and seawater solution, along with long-term stability.^[21] The NO₃⁻-rich passivating layer is responsible for repelling Cl⁻ that results in resistance to corrosion. The MoO₄²⁻-modulated nickel-iron oxide anode NiMoFe/N was reported to display slow degradation during its operation over 1500 h at a current density of 100 mA cm⁻² in 1 M KOH and 0.5 M NaCl.^[22a] As a result of oxidation and reconstruction in the anodic bias, the surface Mo species in this material are transformed to MoO₄²⁻ that is stable in Cl⁻ containing environments. Furthermore, selenized NiFe layered double hydroxide (LDH) also exhibits extraordinary stability for >250 h in 1 M KOH and 1 M NaCl, owing to the presence of large SeO_x⁻ at the electrode surface.^[23a] In another study in this area, Li et al. designed a multilayered electrode containing an outmost oxidized NiFeB_x surface layer, NiFeB_x alloy interlayer and the NiFe alloy substrate.^[24b] BO₂⁻ present at the surface of the electrode is conducive to preventing Cl⁻ corrosion in saline water.

Preferential OH⁻ Adsorption

Initiation and subsequent evolution of the CER or OER involves adsorption and desorption of various reactive intermediates. For example, the first step in these respective processes takes place through adsorption of Cl⁻ and OH⁻. Thus, to avoid interference arising from Cl⁻, an electrocatalyst needs to possess active sites that preferentially adsorb OH⁻ (Figure 3b). To address this issue, Huang et al. designed a Co- and Fe- modified nickel phosphide (CoFe-Ni₂P) for efficient SWS, in which the CoFe-NiOOH species generated in situ serve as selective OH⁻ adsorption sites.^[25] The selectivity is a consequence of the difference between the Gibbs free energy for *Cl and *OH (ΔG^{*Cl*OH}). Theoretical calculations showed that the ΔG^{*Cl*OH} of CoFe-

NiOOH is exceptionally large so as to lessen competitive Cl^- absorption and the undesirable CER. Similarly, NiFe-LDH is also proved to show high OER selectivity by Strasser's group.^[1d, 19d]

In addition to its capture from electrolyte, OH^- can also form by splitting water molecules. Focusing on the OER side of water splitting in neutral media, Sargent and co-workers designed an electrocatalyst in which the strong proton adsorption (SPA)

Figure 3. Rational design strategies toward durable anodic oxygen evolution reaction (OER) catalysts or interfaces for SWS. Shown are strategies of a, b) surface repulsion of Cl^- , c, d) chemically inertness to Cl^- , and e, f) selective absorption of Cl^- . SPA: strong-proton-adsorption materials, HLA: hard Lewis acid, V_{Cl} : Cl vacancy, uSS: unspecific site, SS: specific site.

species, Pd, is incorporated into a Co_3O_4 framework.^[26] This material induces electrolysis using a 370 mV overpotential at 10 mA cm^{-2} and it has >450 h durability at a constant current density of 200 mA cm^{-2} in pH-neutral seawater. The incorporation of SPA cations accelerates the rate-determining water dissociation step in the OER pathway in SWS, offering progress on the path to direct seawater utilization.

In addition, Pearson's hard-soft acid-base (HSAB) principles suggest that OH^- can also be captured by a hard Lewis acid (HLA) layer.^[27] For example, Guo et al. found that introduction of a HLA layer, such as Cr_2O_3 , enables the electrocatalyst CoO_x to split water molecules and capture OH^- directly in natural seawater that is not alkalized nor acidified.^[28] This composite achieves

long-term stability exceeding 100 h at 500 mA cm⁻², a performance similar to that of a typical PEM electrolyzer operating in high-purity water. Specifically, Cr₂O₃ was employed as the layer in this system because Cr³⁺, the hardest Lewis acid among transition metals, ionizes adsorbed water on the surface to generate a high local concentration of OH⁻. Moreover, the measured concentration of OH⁻ on the electrode surface is higher than that required to resist Cl⁻, indicating that the HLA layer causes preferential enrichment of OH⁻. Very recently, Mn species are also proved to act as the HLA sites to strongly bind with OH⁻ and prevent the Cl⁻ attack.^[29] These studies indicated that introduction of a HLA layer might be a general strategy for promoting direct seawater electrolysis by a variety of different catalysts without the need for special engineering.

3.2. Chemically Inertness to Cl⁻

Employing anti-corrosion materials

Studies in the chlor-alkali industry suggest that transition metals, such as Ti^[30] and Ru^[31], have good resistance to corrosion in seawater (Figure 3c). In 2017, a series of Ti foil-supported PtM (M=Fe, Co, Ni, Pd) binary alloy electrodes for OER in real seawater (pH=6.64) were described.^[30a] For example, a Ti supported PtPd electrode exhibits a minimal onset potential of 68 mV, and only a 1.5% current density reduction over 12 h of operation. Choosing an appropriate substrate is key for creating electrodes that are stable during electrolysis in a medium containing Cl⁻. Komiya et al. carried out an investigation to identify electrode substrates that are suitable for the OER at the CoFeO_xH_y electrode in the presence of Cl⁻ in near-neutral medium.^[30c] A comparison of the corrosion behaviour showed that, in contrast to NF, Ti-based materials do not undergo noticeable corrosion in Cl⁻-containing aqueous solution. The fabricated CoFeO_xH_y/Ti electrode was found to operate at 500 mA cm⁻² for 24 h at the low potential of 1.67 V (vs. reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) at 353 K). Fu et al. also designed a 2D self-supporting electrode that has excellent stability for high-efficiency seawater electrolysis.^[30b] In the system, TiO₂ nanorods are supported on a corrosion-resistant Ti plate (Ti/TiO₂) as the substrate and NiB_x catalytic materials were deposited gently on the layer. Chronopotentiometric measurements over 72 h showed that this material undergoes no significant performance degradation. Nanosized RuO₂ with interfacial C has also been observed to have high resistance to corrosion during pH-universal overall SWS.^[31a] Owing to the intrinsic anti-corrosion properties of RuO₂, an electrolyzer with this electrocatalyst has a current density of 10 mA cm⁻² at a cell voltage of 1.52 V, and excellent durability for up to 100 h in 1 M KOH and seawater.

Metal nitrides (MNs) are usually crystalline and possess strong metal-nitrogen bonds, which give them high structural stability and chemical inertness.^[32] These inherent properties make MNs resistant to corrosion and impurities, and therefore, applicable as catalysts for SWS. For instance, Ren's group described 3D NiMoN@NiFeN nanorods supported on NF, which serves as an eminently active and durable OER catalyst for alkaline seawater electrolysis.^[33] It achieved the industrially required current density of 1000 mA cm⁻² at the record low voltage of 1.709 V, as well as 100 h durability at 500 mA cm⁻² in 1 M KOH and seawater. The outer NiFeN nanoparticles in situ evolve to thin amorphous layers of NiFe oxides and NiFe oxy(hydroxide), which are responsible for corrosion resistance to Cl⁻ anions in seawater.

Fabricating protective layers

In addition to relying on anti-corrosion materials, a promising approach to inhibit Cl^- corrosion involves introducing a protective layer which allows selective transfer of OH^- and blocks penetration of Cl^- (Figure 3d). Inspired by the majority of researches on competition between OER and CER, electrodes that show high OER selectivity in acidic solutions are desirable candidates for seawater electrolysis. For example, Bennet,^[34] showed that MnO_x possesses a strong propensity to evolve O_2 from acidic saline water. In 2018, Koper and co-workers investigated the OER and CER selectivity of thin films of MnO_x on IrO_x in aqueous chloride solutions at pH ca. 0.9.^[35] The catalytically inert MnO_x coating in this material functions as a porous layer that prevents Cl^- penetrating while enabling transport of H_2O , protons and O_2 . This study shed a light on the use of a permselective barrier to achieve highly efficient SWS. However, considerations given to the dissolution of Mn ions in flowing electrolytes and instability at extremely low local pHs that might arise at the anode under large current densities, led Esposito to develop an ultrathin semipermeable layer of SiO_x as alternative electrocatalyst coating for selective blocking Cl^- transport.^[36] The nanoscopic SiO_x overlayers cause a marked suppression of the CER at overpotentials over 500 mV than OER. Furthermore, the SiO_x overlayers have robust stability under prolonged operation in acidic solution at high overpotentials. Furthermore, PbO_x ^[37], CeO_x ^[38] and carbon-based materials^[39] have also been devised to prevent Cl^- penetration.

3.3. Selective Adsorption of Cl^-

Most studies aimed at improving the operation of OER catalysts in seawater focus on the repulsion of the Cl^- to reduce its negative effects. However, less attention has been given to uncovering ways to utilize properties of Cl^- to improve the durability of anodes for SWS in seawater.

Immobilizing Cl^- on the surface of electrocatalysts

By forming insoluble chlorides, such as AgCl , Cl^- can be immobilized near anode surfaces (Figure 3e). Recently, Xu et al. proposed a surface chloride immobilization (SCI) strategy and demonstrated its effectiveness in improving the durability of anodes for SWS.^[40] In this effort, an optimized Ag-NiFe-LDH electrode was fabricated by chemically depositing Ag nanoparticles on NiFe-LDH substrate. The composite has impressive long-term stability at 400 mA cm^{-2} in 1 M NaOH and seawater for over 2500 h. In the SCI mechanism, the in situ formation of AgCl on the catalyst surface by combining free Cl^- with oxidized Ag species was key to prevent corrosion. The immobilized Cl^- in AgCl subsequently repels free Cl^- through a common-ion effect. More importantly, this SCI strategy was verified to be general applicable by applying it to another different material.

Another novel strategy to avoid deactivation of electrode materials in seawater involves immobilization of Cl^- in suitable sites, such as vacancies, on the electrocatalyst. Inspired by the finding that reconstruction of $\text{Co}_2(\text{OH})_3\text{Cl}$ electrocatalyst occurs during OER process owing to lattice Cl^- leaching, Zhuang et al. proposed that vacancies freed by Cl^- leaching could act as suitable sites for electrolyte Cl^- incorporation.^[41] The balance between lattice Cl^- leaching and

electrolyte Cl^- incorporation enables avoidance of lattice distortion. Thus, the $\text{Co}_2(\text{OH})_3\text{Cl}$ electrocatalyst should have long-term stability in SWS. Experimental studies indicate that, compared to lattice Cl^- free $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$, the $\text{Co}_2(\text{OH})_3\text{Cl}$ electrocatalyst maintains 99.9% of its initial current density after 60000 s operation while that of $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ decays by 52.7% in 7000 s in 1 M KOH and 0.6 M NaCl solution.

Tailoring Cl^- adsorption sites

One of the causes of the negative corrosion effects of Cl^- is the strong coordination interaction of this ion with active sites of electrocatalysts. Thus, adsorption of Cl^- to inactive sites is a possible approach to reduce this detrimental phenomenon (Figure 3f). Recently, Qiao and co-workers constructed an industrial-scale alkaline electrolyzer with a NiFe-LDH anode that has long term (over 100 h) stability during SWS under a current density of 200 mA cm^{-2} .^[42] Differing from well-known view that Cl^- harms electrocatalysts, this effort observed that Cl^- is beneficial for OER activity and stability of NiFe-LDH. The nature of the interaction of Cl^- with the active sites of the anode can be assessed by comparing the valences of Ni and Fe during the OER. After addition of Cl^- to the material in alkaline pure water, the valence of active Ni sites increases to $>3+$ while that of inactive Fe is lowered. More importantly, Fe-Cl rather than Ni-Cl bonds are formed in this situation. According to the classic HSAB principle, Fe^{3+} , which is a softer Lewis acid than Ni^{4+} , prefers to bind to Cl^- , which is a softer base than OH^- . In this way, adsorption of Cl^- at Fe sites stabilizes the valence of Fe and protects it from OH^- attack, thereby inhibiting its leaching and promoting long-term stability. Furthermore, results of ^{18}O isotope-labeling experiments reveal that participation by lattice oxygen is suppressed by Cl^- in alkaline seawater via the adsorbate evolution mechanism. Blocking this participation accounts for the enhanced stability and activity of the material in seawater.

Very recently, Duan et al. also demonstrated that adsorption of Cl^- in active sites is governed by a single Ir atom bound on the electrocatalyst CoFe-LDH, which leads to remarkable OER activity in 6 M NaOH and 2.8 M NaCl, along with 100% catalytic activity and stability at high current densities ($400\text{--}800 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) over 1000 h.^[43] Compared to that of the catalyst in an aqueous NaOH electrolyte, the current density of Ir-CoFe-LDH increased from 36 mA cm^{-2} to 85 mA cm^{-2} at a voltage of 1.49 V (vs. RHE) when NaCl is present. *Operando* characterizations and density functional theory calculations substantiate that the abundant quantity of Cl^- in seawater dynamically regulates the coordination state of a single-atom of Ir during the OER and effectively maintains a high energy barrier for the CER. Strong Ir-Cl coordination stabilizes CoFe sites, and thereby inhibits Cl^- coordination with both metal sites which leads to increased stability during SWS.

4. Rational Design Strategies toward Durable HER Catalysts/Interfaces for SWS

Most studies of HER electrocatalysts have been performed using surrogate seawater, which is comprised of mixtures of either an alkaline electrolyte with NaCl or an alkaline electrolyte with natural seawater. It should be noted that even when natural seawater is used, addition of a base (e.g., KOH) causes precipitation of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} hydroxides. In these cases, the main concern is corrosion caused by Cl^- . So, rational design strategies for OER electrocatalysts/interfaces are practicable. However, more and more researchers have realized the bridge between surrogate seawater and real seawater. In real seawater, in addition to the Cl^- corrosion, the precipitation of $\text{Mg}^{2+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ at the cathode can heavily degrade the performance. Some articles have reported the decreased HER performance due to the white precipitate on the electrode after only 20 h durability test. To refresh the electrode, acid treatment is performed. For example, Lv et al. soaked the cathode with $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2/\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ precipitation in low concentration of acid (0.05 M HCl) for 30 min, regaining former activity.^[44] Furthermore, researchers also explore the possibility of utilizing abundant Mg^{2+} to co-electrosynthesize high-valued $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ from real seawater. In this section, strategies addressing Cl^- corrosion and addressing Mg/Ca hydroxides precipitation (including inhibiting binding of OH^- to Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} , inhibiting adherence of Mg and Ca hydroxides precipitation, and co-electrosynthesis of nano-sized Mg hydroxides) are summarized (Figure 4). Detailed electrolyte conditions for “seawater” are also given.

4.1. Addressing Cl^- Corrosion

Differing from corrosion of OER catalysts caused by the competing CER, degradation of HER electrocatalysts arises from strong coordination of Cl^- to metals.^[45] Therefore, rational designs of HER electrocatalysts utilize strategies that maximize inhibition of Cl^- binding by inducing passivating anion layers, fabricating protective layers and employing non-corrosive materials. For example, Xu et al. presented a $\text{Cu}_2\text{S}@\text{NiS}@\text{Ni}/\text{NiMo}$ electrode which exhibited high HER activity with 250 mV overpotential at 1000 mA cm^{-2} and superior durability over 2000 h at 500 mA cm^{-2} in 1 M NaOH + seawater (Figure 4a). The NiS layer served as the sulfur source for the formation of polyanion-rich passivating layers, which effectively resist Cl^- corrosion.^[44] Besides, the Ni_3N nanosheets coated by a few-layer carbon shell on NF ($\text{Ni}_3\text{N}@\text{C}/\text{NF}$) was prepared as an efficient and durable electrocatalyst for SWS (Figure 4b).^[46] The protective effect of carbon shell and the intrinsic corrosion resistance of MNs effectively protects Ni_3N from poisoning and corrosion by Cl^- . As a result, $\text{Ni}_3\text{N}@\text{C}/\text{NF}$ operates at a low overpotential of 142 mV at 100 mA cm^{-2} , and has high durability over 100 h in 1 M KOH + seawater. Furthermore, Jin et al. reported a nitrogen-rich Mo_5N_6 with high durability of 100 h at an overpotential of 300 mV in seawater (Figure 4c).^[47] The abundant strong metal-nitrogen bonds and the high valence state of Mo atoms confer structure stability to Mo_5N_6 , making it resistant to harmful Cl^- ions.

4.2. Addressing Mg and Ca Hydroxides Precipitation

Inhibiting binding of OH⁻ to Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺

The Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ ion-induced hydroxide precipitation at the cathode is a major problem associated with SWS of realistic feeds. However, only a few studies have addressed this issue. In one effort, Guo et al. showed that OH⁻ can be captured by an introduced HLA layer, such as Cr₂O₃ or TiO₂ (Figure 4d).^[28] When a Cr₂O₃-CoO_x layer and a current density of 100 mA cm⁻² are utilized, the pH value of bulk seawater is ca. 8.5, which is lower than the value needed to precipitate Mg²⁺/Ca²⁺. Furthermore, the catalyst exhibits excellent stability for 100 h without obvious decay in the PEM electrolyzer. This result is in line with the expectation that the strong binding of OH⁻ to Cr₂O₃ restricts generation of OH⁻ within the electrical double layer (EDL). SWS promoted by Cr₂O₃-CoO_x stably produces H₂ from natural seawater collected from the surface of Huanghai Sea in China (autumn) and then filtered to remove solids and microorganisms. Besides, V₂O₅ and Mn single atom have also been devised to act as HLA sites, which enable strong binding with OH⁻ on the electrode surface, and mitigate the Mg/Ca hydroxides precipitation.^[29, 48]

Analogous to surface repulsion of Cl⁻ at the anode, 1,8-bis(dimethylamino)naphthalene (DMAN) that acts as a proton sponge was introduced to repulse Mg²⁺/Ca²⁺.^[49] By mixing commercial Pt/C and DMAN, the precipitation was alleviated in real seawater. However, the anti-precipitation ability is restricted and it is important to consider whether the positively charged cathode hinders the release of OH⁻ ions from the electrode surface.

Inhibiting adherence of Mg and Ca hydroxides precipitation

Apart from that, physical methods were also applied effectively to address the issue of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺ precipitation. Liang et al. introduced external fluid flows (water flow) to disrupt OH⁻ gradient in situ generated from the reduction process and carried away the large precipitates near the cathode.^[49] Very recently, they further proposed a novel microscopic bubble/precipitate traffic system by constructing ordered honeycomb-like 3D structure with longitudinally arranged/elongated micro-channels for robust anti-precipitation SWS (Figure 4e).^[50] Compared to other porous electrodes with disordered pores like NF, this ordered cathode modestly releases massive and uniform small-sized bubbles on every corner, which provides buoyancy as well as additional forces from bubbles burst to clear itself.^[51] The optimal cathode could stably function under industrially-relevant current density of 500 mA cm⁻² for 150 h in real seawater with near-100% H₂ Faradic efficiency.

In addition, the effects of other cations such as Na⁺ and K⁺ have received little attention. Recently, we observed that Na⁺ in the electrolyte induces selective hydrogen ion adsorption on defective C₃N₄ by tuning the charge distribution between Na⁺ and active sites. This phenomenon enhances photocatalytic H₂ production in seawater.^[52] This finding suggests that it would be worthwhile to explore the effects of other metal cations on SWS.

Co-electrosynthesis of nano-sized Mg hydroxides

Similar to the developed strategies towards OER electrocatalysts, researchers have paid attention to utilization of abundant Mg^{2+} in seawater to electro-synthesize valuable nanoscale $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ sustainably. For example, Lu and co-workers devised a solidophobic surface of NiCu alloy coated with Pt, which achieved unprecedented durability of over 1000 h in simulated electrolyte (0.3 M MgCl_2 + 0.03 M MgSO_4 + 0.06 M CaCl_2) (Figure 4f).^[53] More importantly, this electrode enables H_2 and high-purity $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ production simultaneously. The solidophobic property introduces a dense layer of adsorbed water which forces $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ to nucleate homogeneously in the electrolyte and prevents the contact to the electrode surface. Furthermore, a novel electrolyzer was constructed using seawater as the catholyte and 0.5 M Na_2SO_4 as the anolyte. To facilitate the exit of solid $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, turbulence was enhanced by optimizing the channel structure of the polar plates. Accompanied by H_2 production, 19.07 g of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ with purity exceeding 99.0% was obtained after electrolyzing 20 L of seawater.

Without alkali additives to produce valuable H_2 and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$, this technology will revolutionarily increase the economic viability for seawater electrolysis. However, how to design electrolyzers that allow steady collection of $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ needs to be further focused. Liang et al. has proposed several possible potential solutions, such as providing linear flow channels and regular acid flow pickling, and is already working on them.^[49]

5. Methods for Synthesis of Electrocatalysts/Electrodes

Most SWS electrocatalysts/electrodes developed thus far are in the forms of powders or metal foam (MF)/carbon cloth (CC). In this section, we discuss four methods that have been devised for the preparation of both electrocatalyst powders and electrodes, which can be employed separately or in assemblies. Summaries of the synthetic methods are given in Figure 5 and Table 1–3 along with data comparing the durability of recent HER, OER and bifunctional electrocatalysts/electrodes in seawater.

5.1. Hydrothermal/Solvothermal Method

The hydrothermal/solvothermal method is widely used to synthesize catalyst materials by subjecting them to controlled temperatures (100–300 °C) at autogenous pressures within a liquid medium. During hydrothermal/solvothermal process, reactants dissolve into ions or molecular groups, then react and reprecipitate to form desired products. In this approach, the morphology, surface structure, crystallinity and composition of catalysts can be precisely controlled by manipulating parameters, such as feed ratios, temperature, pressure, time and solvent. Fine-tuned morphology can increase the active area of catalysts, providing a mass of accessible active sites for reactions. By exposing specific crystal facets, catalysts show different reaction selectivity. The increased crystallinity induced by hydrothermal/solvothermal contributes to rapid charge transfer and benefits the stability. Besides, optimized chemical composition is easily tuned by changing certain parameters. For example, the CoFe-LDH@GQDs was synthesized using a hydrothermal method by tuning the concentration of reactants.^[4e] The hydrothermal method can effectively prepare LDHs with uniformity, high purity and good crystallinity.^[54] Besides, the optimized Co:Fe ratio of 2:2 was shown to have the highest activity by tuning the host layer charge.^[55] Also, Yang et al. utilized the reducibility of ethylene glycol at high temperatures to prepare a Ru electrocatalyst whose surface electronic structure was then modulated by using black phosphorus and thus promoting the HER in alkaline seawater.^[56]

Figure 4. Rational design strategies toward durable hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) catalysts or interfaces for SWS. HLA: hard Lewis acid, EDL: electrical double layer, PC: pinewood-derived carbon. a) TEM image of $\text{Cu}_2\text{S@NiS@Ni/NiMo}$. Reproduced from Ref. [4d] with permission. Copyright 2023, Wiley. b) TEM image of $\text{Ni}_3\text{N@C/NF}$. Reproduced from Ref. [46] with permission. Copyright 2021, the Royal Society of Chemistry. c) TEM image of Mo_5N_6 . Reproduced from Ref. [47] with permission. Copyright 2018, American Chemical Society. d) TEM image and pH values of bulk seawater around $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3\text{-CoO}_x$ cathode. Reproduced from Ref. [28] with permission. Copyright 2024, Springer Nature. e) TEM images and digital photos of NiCoP/PC . Reproduced from Ref. [50]

with permission. Copyright 2024, Springer Nature. f) Optical images of NiCu alloy and Mg(OH)₂ product, and XRD spectrum of Mg(OH)₂. Reproduced from Ref. [53] with permission. Copyright 2024, American Chemical Society.

5.2. Support/Chemical Precipitation

The support/chemical precipitation method is the most simple and convenient approach employed to synthesize electrocatalysts/electrodes by facilely tuning temperature, concentration, pH and feed sequence. The technique is mostly used to modify electrodes by creating 3D structures over small areas of supports such as MF and CC.^[57] In this process, soaking the support in a solution of the metal salt for various times enables the metal to penetrate the support through various interactions such as adsorption and surface tension. In an example of this technique, Ren and co-workers devised a one-step approach to grow highly porous S-(NiFe)OOH catalysts on NF over a short time period at room temperature (RT).^[58] Unlike traditional hydrothermal method, the NF directly reacts with the solution and is quickly etched to produce (NiFe)OOH layer, which guarantees highly robust contact, and thus contributes to rapid electron transfer and good stability.

It should be noted that supports utilized in this technique need to be pretreated. Also, the precipitation method efficiently creates nanostructured materials as powdery solids from mixed precursor solutions. Uniform nanoparticles are usually synthesized by using a homogenous precipitation reaction, a process that involves formation and growth of the nucleus.^[59] In addition, by controlling difference between the rates of formation and growth, the material can be produced in crystalline or amorphous forms. For instance, amorphous NiFe-LDH could be formed by mixing Ni²⁺, Fe³⁺ salt solution and NH₄HCO₃ solution at RT.^[60] Different from highly crystalline LDH synthesized by hydrothermal method, this co-precipitation method enables fast nucleation and growth, resulting in amorphous structure.^[61] The disordered structure provides more catalytic sites for OER as well as unaffected barrier to Cl⁻.

5.3. Thermal Treatment

Thermal treatment, which consists of annealing, calcination, carbonization, pyrolysis or thermal shock, is also a versatile technique employed for fabrication of electrocatalysts/electrodes. Upon being subjected to elevated temperature, catalyst materials undergo internal stress relief that eliminates defects and/or releases volatile species. This process modulates the surface morphology and composition, enhances crystallinity, and generates a carbon-framework in the material.^[62] The changes in surface morphology and composition can significantly affect factors such as surface area, roughness, and the exposure of specific crystal facets, thereby influencing the catalytic performance. Enhanced crystallinity shows well-defined crystal structure, which contributes to improved thermal stability and can influence the activity. The carbon-based materials obtained from thermal treatment usually possess abundant surface sites and high conductivity, which enables efficient mass transfer and charge transfer. For example, Shen et al. fabricated RuCoBO nanoparticles by annealing amorphous RuCo precursor at a temperature gradient of 200–400 °C under Ar atmosphere.^[63] As temperature rises, the crystallinity increases

and oxidation phase is formed. The optimized bifunctional electrocatalyst has a moderate crystallinity and exhibits the best activity and durability. Furthermore, other types of materials can be generated by employing different carrier gases, such as NH_3 , air and H_2/Ar , in the thermal treatment process. The use of NH_3 facilitates nitridation process, generating N-doped structure or nitrides that modify the electronic properties. Treatments in H_2 atmosphere facilitate surface reduction reactions and usually enhance HER performance. For example, Qiao's group fabricated a nickel nitride surface (NiN@C) via incomplete nitridation process under NH_3 atmosphere.^[64] This process limits the Ni–N bonding in the bulk structure, while forming the unique unsaturated Ni–N bonding on the surface. Owing to this, NiN@C shows Pt-like HER behavior in 1 M KOH and seawater, and it is corrosion resistant. It is important to note that success of the thermal treatment technique is highly dependent on careful control of the temperature and duration of the heating process.

5.4. Electrochemical Treatment

Electrochemical treatment methods, including electrodeposition, electro-activation and electrooxidation, are promising methods for preparation of electrocatalysts/electrodes because they are scalable, efficient and economical. Because electrochemical treatment is influenced by many parameters, such as potential, current density, ingredient and pH of electrolyte and temperature, it can be precisely controlled to install different properties into catalysts. Electrodeposition enables rapid and controlled growth of various components on the surface of MF or CC. For instance, a core-shell-structured $\text{CoP}_x@\text{FeOOH}$ was produced for promoting the selective OER in seawater by electrodepositing OER-active FeOOH on the surface of the CoP_x .^[65] By electrodeposition, the precise growth of FeOOH layer was controlled to ensure the favorable core-shell structure.

Electro-activation involves modification of surface structures and generation/enhancement of active species while, at the same time, preserving the inside bulk phase. Surfaces of transition metal-based materials are usually electrooxidized during the OER to create their higher oxidation states, which facilitates the multi-electron transfer. For example, an amorphous layer of oxidized NiFeB (i.e., BO_2^- , Ni^{2+} and Fe^{3+}) is installed outside of an NiFeB_x interlayer by using electro-activation.^[24b] The higher valence state of Ni, Fe in situ formed is the catalytic phase and BO_2^- contributes to the corrosion resistance. At the cathode for HER, the enhanced electrocatalytic performances also emerge but much less than those for OER. An example of this effect is found in studies by Lu et al. which show that applying an overpotential of 170 mV to a MnO-NiO-Ni/NF electrode for at least 20 h creates an electro-activated Mn-NiO-Ni/NF electrode that has exceptional HER stability for up to 14 h in natural seawater.^[66] Under the negative bias, the Mn species that doped to NiO-Ni heterostructure was reduced to metallic phase, while the undoped Mn species dissolved drastically. After dissolution and phase transformation, the actual active sites expose for durable HER.

Figure 5. Summary of synthesis methods of electrocatalysts/electrodes for seawater electrolysis. MT: methanol alcohol, DMF: N,N-dimethylformamide, DG: diethylene glycol, EG: ethylene glycol, RT: room temperature. a) HAADF-STEM image of CoFe-LDH. Reproduced from Ref. [4e] with permission. Copyright 2024, Springer Nature. b) SEM image of S-(Ni,Fe)OOH. Reproduced from Ref. [58] with permission. Copyright 2020, the Royal Society of Chemistry. c) Inverse FFT image of RuCoBO. Reproduced from Ref. [63] with permission. Copyright 2023, American Chemical Society; HRTEM image of NiN@C. Reproduced from Ref. [64] with permission. Copyright 2021, Wiley. d) HRTEM image of CoP_x@FeOOH. Reproduced from Ref. [65] with permission. Copyright 2021, ELSEVIER; HRTEM image of NiFeB_x-NiFe. Reproduced from Ref. [24b] with permission. Copyright 2021, Wiley.

Electrooxidation happens when the electrodes work as anode and has been mostly applied for OER electrocatalytic materials in alkaline condition. Under anodic potentials, the metal is oxidized to a higher valence state, which can facilitate the multi-electron transfer of water oxidation.^[67] Depending on the desired level of optimum performance, the electrooxidation time for activation varies from a few minutes to 20 h.

Table 1. Methods for synthesis and durability performance comparisons of recent HER electrocatalysts/electrodes in seawater electrolytes (AWE: alkaline water electrolyzer; J represents a certain current density. For example, J_{10} represents under the current density of 10 mA cm^{-2}).

	Electrocatalyst/electrode	Synthesis method	Electrolyzer type	Electrolyte	Durability (h)	Strategy toward durable catalysts/interfaces	Refs.
Noble-metal based materials	PtNi ₅ /Ti	precipitation	batch-type cell	seawater, pH=6.64	12@-1.2 V	employing anti-corrosion materials	[68]
	Pt-NiTe/NF ^[a]	hydrothermal + soaking	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	27.7@ J_{10}	employing anti-corrosion materials	[69]
	PtNiCu	solvothermal	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 3.5 wt% NaCl	20@ J_{10}	not referred to	[70]
	PtNiCu	Electrodeposition + calcination	batch-type cell & AEMWE	0.3 M MgCl ₂ + 0.03 M MgSO ₄ + 0.06 M CaCl ₂ &	>1000@ J_{100} & >100@ J_{1000}	co-electrosynthesis of nano-sized Mg hydroxides	[53]

			0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄ , seawater			
PtNi/BiVO ₄	precipitation	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	20@J ₁₀	not referred to	[71]
PtNi/CdS	solvothrmal + precipitation	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 3.5 wt% NaCl	4.1@J ₁₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[72]
PtNiN@V ₂ O ₅	hydrothrmal + annealing +	batch-type cell & AEMWE	1 M KOH + seawater	500@J ₅₀₀ & 100@J ₅₀₀	Inhibiting binding of OH ⁻ to Mg ²⁺ and Ca ²⁺	[48]
Pt/MXene	annealing	batch-type cell	seawater, pH=8.28	250@J ₁₀	not referred to	[73]
PtRuMo/Ti	electrodeposition	batch-type cell	seawater	172@-800 mV	employing anti-corrosion materials	[74]
Pt-CoP/CC ^[b]	electrodeposition + annealing + soaking	batch-type cell	seawater	24@J ₁₀	not referred to	[75]
Ru/BP/G ^[c]	solvothrmal	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	1000 cycles	employing anti-corrosion materials	[56]
NiRuIr/G	solvothrmal + annealing	batch-type cell	seawater	200@-230 mV	employing anti-	[76]

	RuCoMo _x /Ti	electrodeposition	batch-type cell	seawater	12@-1.2 V	corrosion materials employing anti-corrosion materials	[77]
	Rh/GDY ^[d]	precipitation	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl	30@J ₁₀₀₀	not referred to	[78]
	Os/GDY	solvothermal	PEMWE	1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl	800@J ₅₀₀	not referred to	[4f]
Non-noble metal alloy	CoNi/Ti	electrodeposition	batch-type cell	seawater	>10@-1.0 V	employing anti-corrosion materials	[79]
Non-noble metal oxides	Mn-NiO-Ni/NF	hydrothermal + annealing + electro-activation	batch-type cell	seawater, pH=8.2	14@-140 mV	not referred to	[66]
Non-noble metal sulfides	CoNiS@NC	hydrothermal + annealing +	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	200@J ₁₀₀ ₀	fabricating protective layers	[80]
	Cu ₂ S@NiS@Ni/NiMo	oxidation + hydrothermal + electrodeposition	batch-type cell & AWE	1 M NaOH + seawater	2000@J ₅ ₀₀ & 675@J ₅₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[4d]
Non-noble metal phosphides	CoP/rGO ^[e] /Ti	solvothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + saturated sea salt	60@J ₁₀	employing anti-corrosion materials	[81]

	CoNiP/NF	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	seawater	20@-290 mV	not referred to	[44]
	NiCoP/PC ^[f]	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	seawater	150@J ₅₀₀	inhibiting adherence of Mg and Ca hydroxides precipitation	[50]
	CoMoP@C	pyrolysis	batch-type cell	seawater	10@-500 mV	fabricating protective layers	[82]
	Ni ₅ P ₄ @Ni ^{2+δ} O ₈ (OH) _{2-δ}	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	seawater	40@J _{10/30/50/100}	fabricating protective layers	[83]
	MoP-Mo ₂ C/NPC ^[g]	electrodeposition + pyrolysis	batch-type cell	seawater	16@-385 mV	not referred to	[84]
	NiCoN@Ni _x P@NiCoN	soaking + annealing	batch-type cell	seawater	24@J ₁₀	employing anti-corrosion materials	[85]
Non-noble metal nitrides	NiN@C	hydrothermal + pyrolysis	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	40@-25 mV	employing anti-corrosion materials	[64]
	Ni ₃ N@C/NF	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₅₀₀	employing anti-corrosion materials fabricating protective layers	[46]
	NiN ₃ /NC ^[h]	precipitation + carbonization	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	14@-200 mV	not referred to	[86]

	NiMoN/NF	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₅₀₀	employing anti-corrosion materials	[33]
	Mo ₅ N ₆	annealing	batch-type cell	seawater	100@–300 mV	employing anti-corrosion materials	[47]
Non-noble metal carbides	Co _x Mo _{2-x} C/MXene/NC	precipitation + annealing	batch-type cell	seawater	225@–500 mV	fabricating protective layers	[87]

[a] NF: Ni foam. [b] CC: carbon cloth. [c] G: graphene. [d] GDY: graphdiyne. [e] rGO: reduced graphene oxide. [f] PC: pinewood-derived carbon [g] NPC: N, P co-doped carbon. [h] NC: N-doped carbon.

Table 2. Methods for synthesis and durability performance comparisons of recent OER electrocatalysts/electrodes in seawater electrolytes (AEMWE: anion exchange membrane water electrolyzer; PEMWE: proton exchange membrane water electrolyzer).

	Electrocatalyst /electrode	Synthesis method	Electrolyzer type	Electrolyte	Durability (h)	Strategy toward durable catalysts/interfaces	Refs.
Noble-metal based materials	RuMoNi	hydrothermal + electro-activation	batch-type cell & AEMWE	1 M KOH + seawater	3000@J ₅₀₀ & 240@J ₅₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[4c]
	Pb ₂ Ru ₂ O _{7-x}	hydrothermal	batch-type cell & AEMWE	0.6 M NaCl, pH=14 & 0.6 M NaCl + 0.1 M NaOH	2@J ₁₀ & 5@J ₂₀₀	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[88]

	Ag-NiFe-LDH	hydrothermal + electrodeposition	batch-type cell & AWE	1 M NaOH + seawater	>2500@ J ₄₀₀ & >1200@ J ₄₀₀	immobilizing Cl ⁻ on the surface of electrocatalysts	[40]
	Ir-CoFe-LDH	precipitation	batch-type cell	6 M NaOH + 2.8 M NaCl	1000@J ₈₀₀	tailoring Cl ⁻ adsorption sites	[43]
	Co _{3-x} Pd _x O ₄	electrodeposition + annealing	batch-type cell & AEMWE	seawater	450@J ₂₀₀ & >65@J ₁₀₀	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[26]
Non-noble metal alloy	NiCo	hydrothermal	batch-type cell	seawater	>40@ 1.5 V	not referred to	[89]
	NiFe/G ^[a]	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	2000@J ₁₀₀	fabricating protective layers	[39b]
	NiMoFe/NF ^[b]	thermal shock	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	550@J ₁₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[22a]
Non-noble metal oxides/(oxy)hydroxide	CoFe-LDH	hydrothermal	batch-type cell	sea salt solution, pH~8.0	8@560 mV	tailoring Cl ⁻ adsorption sites	[90]
	CoFe@GQDs ^[c] /NF	hydrothermal	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl	2800@2.0 V	inducing passivating anion layers fabricating protective layers	[4e]

	NiFe-LDH	precipitation	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl	24@J ₁₀₀	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[60]
	NiFe-LDH	hydrothermal	batch-type cell & AWE	1 M KOH + seawater & 30 wt% KOH + seawater	300@J ₂₀₀ & 100@J ₂₀₀	tailoring Cl ⁻ adsorption sites	[42]
	NiFe-LDH	solvothermal	AEMWE	1 M KOH + seawater	>1100@J ₃₀₀	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[7a]
	CoFeO _x H _y /Ti	electrodeposition	batch-type cell	1.0 mol kg ⁻¹ K-borate + 0.5 mol kg ⁻¹ KCl	42@J ₂₀	employing anti-corrosion materials	[30c]
	Ni-FeOOH	soaking	batch-type cell & AEMWE	1 M KOH + seawater	80@J ₁₀₀ & 15@J ₅₀₀	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[91]
Non-noble metal sulfides	S-(Ni,Fe)OOH	soaking	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₁₀₀	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[58]
	NiCoS/NF	hydrothermal	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₁₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[19a]
	NiS _x -Ni/NiFe	hydrothermal + electrodeposition	batch-type cell	1 M KOH +	1000@J ₄₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[4b]

		osition + electro- activation		seawat er			
	NiFe- LDH/Ni@Ni _x S _y	hydrother mal + solvotherm al	AEMWE	1 M KOH + seawat er	100@J ₄₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[19d]
	NiFe- LDH/FeNi ₂ S ₄ /N F	hydrother mal	batch- type cell	1 M KOH + seawat er	>20@1. 501 V	inducing passivating anion layers	[19c]
Non- noble metal phosphi des	CoP _x @FeOOH	hydrother mal + annealing + electrodep osition	batch- type cell	1 M KOH + seawat er	80@J ₅₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[65]
	NaCoFeP ₂ O ₇ /C C ^[d]	hydrother mal + annealing	batch- type cell	0.1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl	100@J ₅₀	not referred to	[92]
	NiN@NiFeP/NF	hydrother mal + annealing + soaking	batch- type cell	1 M KOH + seawat er	100@J ₅₀₀	employing anti-corrosion materials inducing passivating anion layers	[20d]
	CoFe PBA/Co ₂ P	hydrother mal + annealing	batch- type cell	20 wt% NaOH + seawat er	1000@J _{1 000}	inducing passivating anion layers	[20a]
Non- noble metal nitrides	NiFeN@C/NF	hydrother mal + soaking + annealing	batch- type cell	1 M KOH + seawat er	100@J ₅₀₀	employing anti-corrosion materials	[46]

						fabricating protective layers	
	NiMoN@NiFeN	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₅₀₀	employing anti-corrosion materials	[33]
Non-noble metal borides/selenides	B-Co ₂ Fe-LDH	hydrothermal + soaking	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₅₀₀	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[93]
	NiFeB _x -NiFe	annealing + electro-activation	batch-type cell	30 wt% KOH + 0.5 M NaCl	>100@J ₅₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[24b]
	Ni _x B/B ₄ C/NF	soaking + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	24@1.5 0 V	inducing passivating anion layers	[94]
	CoMoSe@FeO OH/NF	hydrothermal	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	160@J ₃₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[22b]
	NiMoSe/NF	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₁₀₀	not referred to	[95]
	Se-NiFe-LDH	hydrothermal + electrodeposition	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 1 M NaCl	80@J ₃₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[23a]
others	(NiFe)C ₂ O ₄ /NF	soaking	batch-type cell & PEMWE	1 M KOH + seawater & 1 M NaOH	600@J ₁₀₀₀ & 150@J ₅₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[18]

				+ seawater		
$\text{Co}_2(\text{OH})_3\text{Cl}$	precipitation	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 0.6 M NaCl	16.6@1.7 V	immobilizing Cl^- on the surface of electrocatalysts	[41]

[a] G: graphene. [b] NF: Ni foam. [c] GQDs: graphene quantum dots. [d] CC: carbon cloth.

Table 3. Methods for synthesis and durability performance comparisons of recent bifunctional electrocatalysts/electrodes in seawater electrolytes.

	Electrocatalyst /electrode	Synthesis method	Electrolyzer type	Electrolyte	Durability (h)	Strategy toward durable catalysis/interfaces	Refs.
noble-metal based materials	PtPd/Ti	electrodeposition	batch-type cell	seawater, pH=6.64	12@2.0 V	employing anti-corrosion materials	[30a]
	RuCoBO	precipitation + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 3.5 wt% NaCl	>220@ $J_{50/100}$	preferential OH^- adsorption	[63]
	RuB	precipitation + annealing	batch-type cell & AEMWE	1 M KOH + 3.5 wt% NaCl	1000@ $J_{10/50/100}$ & 400@ $J_{500/1000}$	inducing passivating anion layers	[96]
	RuMn-NiFe-LDH	hydrothermal	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	250@ J_{650}	preferential OH^- adsorption inhibiting binding of OH^- to Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+}	[29]

non-noble metal oxides/ (oxy)hydroxides	CoO _x -Cr ₂ O ₃	annealing	batch-type cell & PEMWE	seawater	>225@1.9 V & 100@J ₅₀₀	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption inhibiting binding of OH ⁻ to Mg ²⁺ and Ca ²⁺	[28]
	CoFe@PbO _x @Ni/Ti	electrodeposition + calcination	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl	150@J ₅₀₀	fabricating protective layers	[37]
	GO ^[a] @Fe@NiCo(OH)/NF	hydrothermal + annealing + electrodeposition	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl	378@J ₁₀₀₀	fabricating protective layers	[39a]
non-noble metal sulfides	Ni ₃ S ₂ @MoS ₂ @Ni ₃ S ₂ /NF ^[b]	hydrothermal	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₁₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[19b]
	NiCoS@NiFe LDH/NF	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell & AEMWE	1 M KOH + 0.5 M NaCl & 1 M KOH + seawater	>100@J ₂₀₀ & >320@J ₄₀₀ /600	inducing passivating anion layers	[97]
non-noble metal phosphides	CoP-Cr/NF	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	160@J ₁₀₀	employing anti-corrosion materials	[98]
	CoFe-Ni ₂ P/NF	hydrothermal + annealing	batch-type cell & AEMWE	6 M KOH + seawater	100@J ₅₀₀ & >350@J ₁₀₀ 0	preferential OH ⁻ adsorption	[25]

	NiFeP/NF	solvothermal	batch-type cell	1.0 M KOH + 0.01 M KHCO ₃ + 1 M NaCl	500@J ₁₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[99]
	Ni ₂ P-Fe ₂ P/NF	soaking + annealing	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	48@J ₁₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[20c]
non-noble metal nitrides	Ni ₂ P/NiCoN/Fe ₂ P	annealing + soaking	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	40@J ₅₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[21]
non-noble metal selenides	Fe,P-NiSe ₂	electrodeposition + electrooxidation + annealing	AEMWE	seawater	200@J ₈₀₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[20b]
	Se-FeCo-LDH	hydrothermal	batch-type cell	1 M KOH + seawater	245@J ₁₀	inducing passivating anion layers	[23b]

[a] GO: graphene oxide. [b] NF: Ni foam.

6. Design of Electrolyzers

Designing reliable and practical electrolytic cells is an essential component of creating highly efficient SWS systems. At present, the main types of systems for carrying out SWS are alkaline water electrolyzer (AWE), AEM water electrolyzer (AEMWE), PEM water electrolyzer (PEMWE) and high-temperature solid oxide electrolyzer cell (SOEC). Use of these technologies have strict electrolyte requirements, such as ultra-pure, deionized water or 20–30% KOH solution with contaminants below the ppm level. When used in seawater electrolysis, the electrolyzer configurations differ depending on the impurities present in the electrolyte. In these cases, using asymmetric feed method, rationally designing efficient and durable catalyst, and investigating steam from seawater are developed for effective seawater electrolyzers. Besides, some innovative seawater electrolyzers with membrane modified are reported, such as forward osmosis (FO) coupled seawater electrolyzer and self-breathable waterproof membrane integrated seawater electrolyzer. In these cases, well-modified membrane and optimized electrolyzer designs are crucial. The ions selectivity, areas, pore sizes, thickness, hydrophilic/hydrophobic nature of membrane and transmembrane vapor pressure/concentration gradient are factors to be considered. In this section, we focus on the discussion of four innovations made in membrane electrolyzers for SWS.

6.1. Asymmetric Feeds Electrolyzer

Typical seawater electrolyzer uses a symmetric feed of alkalinized seawater to achieve efficiencies comparable to state of the art electrolyzers. However, the alkali additive causes additional costs. Therefore, efficient SWS without using an alkaline additive remains a challenge. In 2020, an asymmetric feed electrolyzer utilizing non-basified seawater was described by Strasser (Figure 6a), which displays high resistance to Cl^- corrosion and selectivity for the OER even at cell potentials $>3.0\text{ V}$.^[19d] This approach enables direct circulation of neutral seawater at the cathode, while circulating pure KOH electrolyte at the anode. In Cl^- containing alkaline electrolyte, NiFe-LDH has superior catalytic activity and OER selectivity compared to those of Ir-based benchmark catalysts. Then in a 2023 study, transition-metal phosphides/chalcogenides were shown to have high potential as highly active and corrosion-resistant PGM-free catalysts for SWS.^[19d] The cell design comprised asymmetric operation with a dry cathode, while anodic Cl^- repulsion was achieved in alkalized seawater thanks to anodic sulfidation, as outlined above. It showed industrially relevant current densities of up to 1.0 A cm^{-2} below 2.0 V cell potential and performed stably for 100 h. Also, Shi et al. designed a pH-asymmetric electrolyzer containing a Na^+ exchange membrane for direct seawater splitting, which blocks transport of Cl^- to the anode and simultaneously prevents Cl^- corrosion and $\text{Mg}^{2+}/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ precipitation.^[100] Utilizing the Na^+ exchange membrane as the separator, Cl^- in the catholyte (natural seawater) is prohibited from entering the anode. The problem of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} precipitation is alleviated in near-neutral seawater ($\text{pH}<9.5$) by employing a flowing electrolyte procedure. Consequently, the electrolyzer reaches 400 mA cm^{-2} at a low voltage of 1.66 V at $80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which corresponds to an electricity cost (US\$1.36 per kg of H_2 , \$0.031/kW h for the electricity bill), that is lower than the United States Department of Energy (DOE) 2025 target of US\$1.4 per kg of H_2 . However, this asymmetric feed

technique requires the use of ion-exchange membranes as well as electrocatalysts with high quality to ensure high efficiency and durability.

Figure 6. Four innovations in membrane electrolyzer. a) Asymmetric feeds electrolyzer. b) Forward osmosis coupled seawater electrolyzer. c) Self-breathable waterproof membrane integrated seawater electrolyzer. d) High-temperature solid oxide seawater electrolyzer. WBM: waterproof breathable membrane.

6.2. Forward Osmosis Coupled Seawater Electrolyzer

Reverse Osmosis (RO) is one of the most popular membrane processes for saline water treatment.^[101] However, the main disadvantage of this technology is high power consumption due to the high pressure that needs to be applied to the RO membrane. Therefore, the more energy effective FO technology has emerged as a low-cost alternative. In 2021, Veroneau and Nocera proposed an electrolyzer design in which water splitting with FO that enables saltwater to be utilized directly without pretreatment or purification while circumventing challenges posed by impurities and energy-wasting side reactions (Figure 6b).^[4h] Nocera's FO water splitting system is composed of a single electrochemical compartment segregated from the impure water source by a semipermeable membrane. The FO water splitting cell is charged with a higher concentration inner electrolyte buffered at pH 7 and is separated from 0.6 M NaCl outer solution using a cellulose acetate semipermeable membrane. Then in 2022, Nocera and co-workers further replaced 0.6 M NaCl outer solution with real seawater without any treatments.^[102] The formed concentration gradient induces flow of water from the saline solution to the more concentrated electrolyte. The concentration gradient is maintained by water splitting, when the rates of forward osmosis and effective water splitting are balanced. Due to an increased selectivity at rejecting Cl^- , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} and CO_2 by the cellulose acetate membrane, the FO SWS system is scalable and applicable to large scale harvesting of H_2 from seawater.

Similarly, continuous ampere-level H_2 production from natural seawater was successfully accomplished in a dual-cation exchange membrane (CEM) electrolyzer.^[103] The monovalent-selective CEMs spatially separate the flowing seawater chamber from bilateral electrolyte (concentrated NaOH) chambers, ensuring the sustainable water supply from seawater without interferences from Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , and Cl^- ions. Such a continuous SWS system equipped with readily available NF could run steadily over 100 h at an industry-relevant current of 1.0 A. It is worth noting that, to move this design to market, guidance from industrially realized technologies such as chlor-alkali production as well as membrane technologies should be further explored in the future.

6.3. Self-breathable Waterproof Membrane Integrated Seawater Electrolyzer

Although, the FO technology has great potential for use in SWS, mutual ion diffusion still occurs between the saline water and the electrolyte during 24–120 h operation, suggesting that the membrane has a non-ideal ion-sieving effect. To ensure that pure water is fully separated from seawater, Xie et al. created a novel direct seawater splitting system for hydrogen production that operates at 250 mA cm^{-2} for >3200 h under practical conditions (Figure 6c).^[4j] The key feature of the design of this system is integration of an in situ water purification process based on a self-driven phase transition mechanism with a seawater electrolysis component, which is accomplished by applying a hydrophobic porous polytetrafluoroethylene-based waterproof and breathable membrane as a gas-path interface and utilizing concentrated KOH solution as a self-dampening electrolyte. In this case, the difference between the water vapor pressure of seawater and KOH electrolyte drives spontaneous seawater evaporation and diffusion through the membrane to KOH side, where it is re-liquified. The hydrophobic property of the membrane

enables avoidance of impurity ions in seawater and the micrometer-scale of the gas diffusion path enables migration of the water vapor. This “liquid-gas-liquid” phase transition-migration process provides a pure water feed created from natural seawater, while prevents impurity ions, such as Cl^- , Mg^{2+} and SO_4^{2-} . Finally, when an equilibrium between the rates of water migration and electrolysis is established, the integrated system operates in a continuous and stable manner to produce H_2 from real seawater.

6.4. High-temperature Solid Oxide Seawater Electrolyzer

In addition to the aforementioned seawater electrolyzers operated under low temperatures, the high-temperature solid oxide seawater electrolyzer which works at high temperatures (800–1000°C) driven by thermal energy was also reported. In high-temperature SOEC, steam evaporated from water and is transported to the cathode to produce H_2 . The generated O^{2-} passes through the solid oxide membrane to the anode to form O_2 .^[104] In 2017, Lim et al. investigated the effects of seawater electrolysis for H_2 production through electrolyzing steam produced from simulated seawater (mainly contains Na^+ , Cl^- , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Br^- , SO_4^{2-}).^[48] It has been found that the electrolysis of pure water steam and seawater steam gave almost the same initial performance and degradation rate. The solid oxide seawater electrolyzer showed durability for up to 70 h under a constant current of 0.8 A cm^{-2} . In addition, at elevated temperature, part of the energy to split the water molecules is supplied in form of heat, which in turn reduces the electrical energy demand. Thus, SOEC has an edge over low-temperature seawater electrolyzers where the cost of H_2 is dominated by electricity costs.^[105] This configuration which produces clean steam feeding from low-grade water source may open up a new sight apart from electrocatalyst/electrode designs. However, there are possible concerns about seawater electrolysis in SOEC, including long-term durability requirement for electrodes as well as the damage of trace impurities from seawater vapor to electrolyzers. Besides, Liu et al. found that there was still ppm salt in the steam and the pipeline or cell could be blocked at some points after 420 h operations.^[106]

Furthermore, the backend gas storage system is at least as important as production processes. However, the current published articles on the seawater electrolyzer do not give the relevant designs. The purpose of storing hydrogen energy is to be safe and efficient, and to be used anywhere and anytime. Referring to commercial water electrolyzer, produced H_2 needs to be separated, washed, cooled and dried before being stored in a gas tank. According to the guidance of Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technologies Office, H_2 can be stored in physical-based method and material-based method.^[107] In physical-based method, H_2 can be stored as either a gas or a liquid, which requires high-pressure tanks or cryogenic temperatures, respectively. Physical storage is the most mature hydrogen storage technology. Besides, H_2 can also be stored on the surfaces of solids (by adsorption) or within solids (by absorption). Material-based storage including sorbents, chemical hydrogen storage materials, and metal hydrides. This method is better than other methods because takes up less volume.^[108] It is open to development and has potential to meet DOE hydrogen storage targets. To sum up, the research progress of seawater electrolysis systems can be summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Overview of seawater electrolysis system. AEM: anion exchange membrane, PEM: proton exchange membrane.

Seawater Electrolysis System	
Separator	Diaphragm/AEM/PEM/HOMEMADE membrane
Catalyst	Typically, metal oxy(hydroxide), metal sulfides/phosphides/nitrides/borides/selenides
Electrolyte	Alkaline seawater/Alkaline simulated seawater/Seawater
Temperature (°C)	20-80
Pressure	Not referred to
Current density (A cm ⁻²)	0.1-1.0
Cell voltage (V)	1.7-2.65
Durability time (h)	70-3200
Backend gas storage	Physical storage/Material-based storage

7. Conclusions and Prospects

Electrochemical SWS powered by renewable energy for the production of green hydrogen promises reduced water pretreatment requirements coupled to reduced foot prints and complexity of balance of plant components of electrolyzer systems. However, due to the complex ionic, biochemical, and biological components of seawater, the direct SWS approach faces serious challenges related to interfacial catalytic activity, electrode durability, and scalability. While many efforts carried out thus far have focused on the design and preparation of electrocatalysts, electrodes or interfaces with sustained high catalytic activity, fewer studies have addressed long-term durability in presence of a complete and realistic set of contaminating chemical cations and anions, and ever fewer have addressed aspects of biochemical and biological contaminants that can lead to biofilm formation and biofouling. Flagship German National Research Initiatives, such as H2Mare, H2Meer, and SeaEly currently strive to address all the challenges above.^[109]

In the future, the following issues need to be taken into closer consideration.

1) Use of standardized test conditions. Electrolytes employed to assess the efficiency and durability of SWS materials or SWS cells should as much as possible match the composition of realistic seawater, such as seawater that has been filtered out of sediment. Otherwise, the simulated seawater should follow the ion concentrations shown in Table 5.^[110] To date, most electrode innovations were tested in electrolytes, in which only NaCl was present. However, such basic NaCl electrolyte is not an adequate surrogate for seawater. For example, not only Cl⁻ but

also Br⁻ can act corrosively at the anode.^[111] Compared to chloride, bromide exhibits faster corrosion kinetics, generating shallow-wide pits on Ni-based anodes, ultimately causing extensive spalling of the catalyst layer. Therefore, in addition to addressing anti-Cl⁻ corrosion, it is essential to design anti-Br⁻ corrosion anodes for seawater electrolysis, especially considering that most current electrode materials are in situ grown on NF. More importantly, the presence of Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ at the cathode results in the formation of insoluble and hence often deactivating carbonate and hydroxide films and coatings due to local pH increases. Moreover, solid impurities and microbial contaminants in seawater also lead to fouling and degradation of electrode surfaces. Thus, in order to fully integrate new electrocatalysts/electrodes/interfaces into SWS, consideration needs to be given to ways of avoiding both halide ion oxidation at the anode and precipitation reactions at the cathode, among other deleterious reactions. Further studies that address in detail the role of specific impurities to electrode durability would be highly beneficial to the community. In addition to using standard criteria to formulate optimal electrolytes, performance evaluation parameters such as current density and duration time should be fully investigated, especially from the point of view of industrial-scale H₂ production. Here, we propose to use electricity consumed per kg of H₂ produced as a criterion for comparison. According to the Multi-Year Program Plan (MYPP) released by the DOE in 2024, the interim cost target for clean H₂ production is \$2 by 2026 and ultimate target of \$1 by 2031.^[6]

Table 5. The concentrations of the major constituents in surface seawater with a salinity of 3.5% at 20 °C.

Species	Conc. [mmol kg ⁻¹]
Cl ⁻	545.87
Na ⁺	469.00
SO ₄ ²⁻	28.235
Mg ²⁺	52.82
Ca ²⁺	10.27
K ⁺	10.21
HCO ₃ ⁻	1.845
Br ⁻	0.842
B(OH) ₃	0.334
B(OH) ₄ ⁻	0.082
CO ₃ ²⁻	0.184
Sr ²⁺	0.090
F ⁻	0.068

2) **Scalable electrode and cell designs.** Attention needs to be given to the design of scalable synthesis methods of catalysts, as well as scalable electrodes and cell preparation techniques. Milligram scale synthesis methods for fabrication of laboratory electrocatalysts/electrodes—a focus in many today’s SWS reports—is an obstacle hindering commercial applications. For industrial electrolyzers, electrode sizes are required to be on the scale of square meters, while typical current seawater electrolysis systems for laboratory explorations have square centimeter or even smaller sizes. Larger-sized SWS cells and stacks will pose new challenges, such as shunt currents, which have to be addressed, as well. At the same time, scaling SWS needs to overcome similar challenges as PEMWE and AEMWE stacks today: Inhomogeneities in the materials specifications of anode porous transport layer and bipolar plate components, associated with inhomogeneous compression across the cell area coupled to plate bending give rise to an undesired distribution of individual cell performance. Also along the lines of today’s PEMWE and AEMWE developments, operation conditions of SWS cells or stacks should move to higher current densities in order to lower capital investment cost of SWS systems. In addition, the current methods developed for preparation of electrodes involve complex steps, which impede pragmatic applications. From this viewpoint, electrodeposition may be a promising synthesis method thanks to its scalability, low cost and tune electrocatalysts/electrodes ability. It should be noted that industrialization of the electrodeposition method, improvement of the uniformity of electrodes and establishing a comprehensive database of essential parameters should be goals of further studies in this area. Designing specialized and continuous equipment of electrodeposition method is also expected.

3) **Designing improved cell or water conditioning membranes.** Advanced functional membranes are crucial for building efficient industrial scale electrolyzers that operate on seawater or low-grade water without the need for extensive purification/treatment step. Common membrane and diaphragm technologies are susceptible to transport and blockage by ions. Thus, a full review and possible reengineering of all aspects and components of today’s electrolyzer technology is needed. Based on the present state of knowledge, AEM electrolyzer appear to be the most likely systems to fulfill these requirements, because generation of free chlorine is suppressed and a wider potential window is available. Wang et al. reviewed the special issues utilizing AEMWE for seawater electrolysis, involving the membrane electrode assembly (MEA)’s design and performance evaluation at the device scale.^[112] An AEM with high OH⁻ conductivity and good chemical/mechanical stability is necessary. Porous transport layer (PTL) needs to improve its transmission performance by adjusting pore size, porosity and optimizing the morphology. Similarly, advanced functional membranes for nano- or ultrafiltration of seawater feed will be critical for water conditioning prior to feeding into the SWS cell or stack. Besides, to steadily collect the co-electrosynthesized Mg(OH)₂, rational design of novel electrolyzer such as employing linear flow channels to avoid precipitate buildup should be focused further.

4) **Integration with intermittent renewable power.** The sustainability of hydrogen production should be an important concern of future investigations of SWS. In renewable energy-rich areas, such as coastal and hyper-arid regions with intense solar irradiation, strong on- and off-shore wind and wave energy sources are ideal for production of renewable electricity. Thus,

electrocatalytic splitting of seawater employing these renewable energy sources as electricity is one of the most promising methods to produce transportable and storable hydrogen. The intermittent nature of renewables requires the design of SWS that operate robustly under transient and dynamic operation conditions. In this regard, accelerated start/stop practical-relevant experiments to verify the adaptability of electrodes in harsh and fluctuated conditions are required. Very recently, Xie and co-workers presented a floating seawater electrolysis system that employed wind energy in wave motion environment. Under real and fluctuating ocean conditions, this system achieved stable operation for over 240 h with an electricity consumption of 5 kWh Nm⁻³ H₂ and high purity (>99.9%) of H₂.^[113]

5) Coupling alternative reactions at the anode. Considering the thermodynamically challenges and sluggish kinetics of OER, as well as the relatively low value of O₂ gas, alternative reactions can be coupled at the anode, which can inhibit the generation of corrosive CER, produce value-added products and reduce electricity costs.^[114] The strategies include: 1) anodic electrolyte substitution for electrolysis of small molecules which are thermodynamically favorable than OER and 2) utilization of abundant Cl⁻ to produce value-added products. At the anode, organic compounds can be upgraded by oxidation or pollutants can be degraded. For example, sulfur oxidation reaction^[115] (SOR, S²⁻ → S + 2e⁻, -0.48 V vs. RHE), ethylene glycol oxidation reaction^[116] (EGOR, CH₂OH-CH₂OH + 10OH⁻ → COO⁻-COO⁻ + 8H₂O + 8e⁻, 0.57 V vs. RHE), and microplastics upgradation^[117] (particularly important for environment protection in the ocean). Additionally, seawater electrolysis can degrade various pollutants into environmentally friendly substances, such as hydrazine degradation^[1a, 118] (HzOR, N₂H₄ + 4OH⁻ → N₂ + 4H₂O + 4e⁻, -0.33 V vs. RHE) and urea degradation^[119] (UOR, CO(NH₂)₂ + 6OH⁻ → N₂ + CO₂ + 5H₂O + 6e⁻, 0.37 V vs. RHE). Given that the electrolysis of sodium chloride solutions to generate chlorine is well-established in the chlor-alkali industry, dimensionally stable anode (DSA) and related systems can be effectively applied to seawater electrolysis for the production of value-added products. Active chlorine can be directly electro-synthesized from natural seawater.^[120] By leveraging Cl⁻ in seawater, the electrooxidation of ethynylbenzenes has been successfully accomplished to produce α,α-dichloroketones, which serve as important intermediates for the synthesis of pharmaceutical compounds.^[121] Furthermore, the selective electrosynthesis of high-value ethylene oxide by chloride-mediated ethylene epoxidation shows tremendous potential to integrate seawater electrolysis with chemical industry.^[122] However, to promote the development of this technique, the match of current and yield between HER and anodic reactions, the separation and purification of products, the design of catalysts and electrolytes, the follow-up treatment of used electrolytes, and the influence to ion exchange membrane need to be considered comprehensively.

Clearly, today direct seawater electrolysis technologies are far from industrial levels. However, over the coming decade their scale and applicability could reach relevant industrial H₂ production levels. Moreover, if advances in seawater electrolysis are expanded to other low-grade water sources, such as groundwater, sewage and industrial wastewater, the problem of water source competition, water scarcity and water quality will be alleviated.

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